

Crafts in Latin America: The contribution of the Fab Labs in the promotion of resilient communities

Pablo C. Herrera, Vanessa Montezuma, Benito Juárez

*Pablo C. Herrera, Universidad Peruana de Ciencias Aplicadas
pablo@espaciosdigitales.org*

*Vanessa Montezuma
vanessa@arquitecturayciudad.com*

*Benito Juárez
beno@fablablima.org*

Lima, Perú

Abstract

We researched the work process between traditional artisans and architects with programming and fabricating skills in Latin America. Kinnunen (2015) proposed that craft inside maker culture must grow resilient against, or adapt to, exogenous forces. In this research, we analysed the contribution of Latin America FabLabs in the context of contemporary making practice with traditional craft, showing as stated by Borges (2015:11), that Latin American craft is produced collectively in adverse conditions and in rural and marginal areas. We conclude that the contribution of algorithmic craft (Jacobs, 2013), digital fabrication and Machines that make (Lassiter, 2013:253) in the Latin American context overcame computerized technologies, which only contributed to the object's presentation (Duque et al. 2005:73). We validated that the renaissance of craft is as promising in Latin America (Borges 2015:14) as in many western countries (Kinnunen, 2015). We state that these cases promote a creative compromise responding to changing conditions in local economy, which also lies at the core of resilience. An impulse, which promotes the opportunity, construction and sustainability of resilient communities, improving and perpetuating in the region, the identity of its designs and its popular traditions, using programming and digital fabrication through the Fab Lab.

Keywords

Latin America, Resilient Community, Fab Labs, Artisans, Digital Craft

1 Introduction

In this research, we started with the question “Who should be resilient, against what, and how?” in the context of Craft beyond craft: the transformative role of craft's resilience, proposed by Kinnunen (2015). We also considered Fountain's affirmation (2013:407) that “Design and making skills – whether rooted in homecraft, studio crafts or workshop crafts – represent a key thread in the manifold knowledge and skills underpinning resilience and adaptability”. We propose, through the revision of case studies, that what links these impulses in Latin America are the Fab Labs. Fountain (2013:409) also stated that “Craft and design merge as interdependent knowledge and skills in the grassroots networks working toward more resilient households and communities”. We have to define, though, how these different knowledge and skills are connected. In Latin America, integration of technologies in the designer's and craftsman's abilities was described by Duque et al. (2005:73), who systematized the implementation of computerized methods to encourage craftsman's creativity, visualization and its contextualization. However, this interaction

© 2018 by Pablo C. Herrera, Vanessa Montezuma, Benito Juárez. – This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. To view a copy of this license, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/> or send a letter to Creative Commons, PO Box 1866, Mountain View, CA 94042, USA.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1344443

between artisans and designers, did not demonstrate a clear difference until the emergence of Fab Labs, which provide designers with tools to surpass the mere representation of the object, and to provide preservation of processes through code (Jacobs, 2013), as well as fabrication and adaptation of their new machines (Lassiter, 2013:253). Fab Labs providing facilities and providing innovation support is a business model proposed by Troxler (2010). In this sense, FAB Academy's systematized learning, mobile installation and other academic centers would boost the construction of resilient communities as an agenda for craftsmanship.

At MIT in 1998, Neil Gershenfeld introduced the class **MAS 863 How to Make (almost) Anything** which, since 2003, this class is part of MIT's Center for Bits and Atoms (Gershenfeld, 2012). In 2009, and funded by the Spanish Government, MIT and IaaC impulse the program **FAB Academy** initiating the world socialization of fabrication technologies as never before.

As we will show in this research, Costa Rica was part of the network in 2002, but in the global south it will be Peru and Ethiopia, who start the implementation outside the USA (Herrera & Juárez, 2013). Gershenfeld (2005) sustain that this approach looks for the boost of local production through the solution of their own problems. According to the different initiatives created by FabLabs, craftsmanship in Latin America starts inside the FabLab network in 2016 (FabLat) and 2017 (FAB13), with different cases associated to local craftsmanship, which are part of this research. To better understand this link, different in the southern and northern hemispheres, one of the objectives is to highlight the differences and similarities that are part of resilience, in moments when the advance of industrialization and international products' trade jeopardizes the identity and continuity of several local traditions.

1.1 Differences between Global South and North

Lindtner & Avle (2017:8) argue that southern economies are similar to the ideals of open code, since they are informal, imitation-based, artisanal and, in the case of China, with a large scale production, or, in the case of Latin America, without serial production. For Borges (2013:11), "In Latin America, it is an activity disseminated mainly throughout countryside areas, but also favelas and fringe areas in the cities, where the artisans make objects collectively as a way of coping with adverse conditions". The region lacks of national regulations for protecting designs, while having a heavy bureaucracy in the processes for patents and utility models and innovation policies, which are overcome by copying, cheap workforce and unfair competition. In addition, FabLabs in Latin America face four adverse factors: economy; management and maintenance; administration and education (Herrera & Juarez, 2013). The same factors are considered by Mboa (2017:82-83) when describing the case of Africanization of the Maker Movement.

For the south, Borges (2011:25) states that these objects "often made collectively (by family and/or neighborhood groups) (...). These techniques many have transmitted through generations of the same family or by one or b elder members of a community (...). They have very rarely been learned at school, even when the artisanal groups belong to the middle class". Herrera (2016

The southern case shows a very clear difference between creation and artisanal production with the northern case. Seo-Zindy & Heeks (2017:13) gathered cases that show that "in the global north, in particular in Europe, tend to focus on how members of workspace communities engage with social issues such as environmental sustainability". Borges (2011:25) from Brazil insists that this craft know-how is different from that of the Northern hemisphere "in which techniques are learned in university courses and are practices by educated people who see in this activity of self-expression –and this brings them closer to art than to design". Waldman-Brown et al. (2013) found clear differences between in the study of Africa's informal sector: Fab Labs has "audience of upper-class academics and hobbyists: well-educated but impractical" in opposed to informal workshops with "audience of lower—class informal artisans: uneducated, crude, and dangerous". In this context, what is produced in a fab lab has all the potential to solve all the limitations described to support the work of an artisanal community.

1.2 Programming and Digital Fabrication

This research explores the design history and work of a generation of Latin American architects and designers specialized in programming and fabrication with traditional artisans. In the 21st century, this scenario was empowered from experiences produced in FabLabs and laboratories in the context of

localisms and neo artisans. We look at how programming and fabrication improves their creativity and processes, focusing on learning and prototyping, adapting to the new economy, strengthening the regional identity in the scene of global design.

The state of the art between craftsmanship and digital fabrication in the global society of the 21st century was documented in a previous research (Herrera, 2016) with emphasis in the improvement of production. In the same research it was highlighted the initiative of some FabLabs, while finding users of visual programming such as Grasshopper of Rhinoceros, supporting craftsmanship's creativity. This computational perspective has precedents in the research of Kornhauser (2002) and Jacobs (2013) from MIT, who created programmed environments to systematize creative processes aiming to empower craftsmanship.

1.3 Artisans, Digital Craft and Makers in the global south

In Latin America (especially in the Andean Region), there are four scenarios where traditional craft is intensively developed. 1) According to García (2004:34), craft is the result of popular indigenous and rural activities. 2) Lauer (1982:64-65) describes an Andean tradition based on pre-colonial cultures (Inca and Maya). 3) Borges (2015:11) describes human nuclei in peripheral areas as an effect of migration from the countryside to the city. 4) According to Sabogal (1974) and Rengifo (1989), from a marketplace's demand which takes original products as references to produce new versions. All of them, with the follow problems: difficult access to internet, opposition to capacitation and the applied technology level in products and processes is limited (DIRCETUR, 2016:10-11) or difficulty to access digital platforms (CNCA, 2017:41). In the 21st century, this scenario is empowered as a result from experiences produced in FabLabs, Makerspaces and laboratories in the context of neo-artisans (Herrera, 2016). Except neo-artisans, all these production was developed with a skill and knowledge that is not explicit, but locked inside their authors.

2 Methodology

The main objective is mapping the coexistence of designers and traditional artisans, providing experiences that could strengthen the identity and history of contemporary design in the region and boosting resilient communities, comparing universalist ideals historically active with popular traditions and local events in a multidisciplinary systematized synergy at Latin America.

In a previous study about programming and digital fabrication between artisans and architects (Herrera, 2016) we identified experiences in Latin America under four groups of initiatives: formative, academic, practice and neo craft. In this investigation, we looked for a way of systematizing the information produced by several projects and experiences in four cases study.

3 Case Studies.

Participants are or were affiliated to a Fab Lab through Fab Academy, with experience leading projects in digital fabrication in deep relation to the artisans' work. We tried to reach a wide range of specialists in this area to get different perspectives on the subject, but when we could not get a response from the participant, the data was obtained from public networks.

3.1 Case Study 1. Artisans non-affiliated to a Fab Lab.

The artisan establish a link with a Fab Lab, rather than choosing an open workshop, in some cases, are initiatives which, through grant funds, public or private, started a project and used a FabLab and its infrastructure as a technological partner.

One case was a SME project directed by Vanessa Roca, where a group of jewelers looked for training at FabLab UNI (Peru) in order to explore new technologies applied to their processes, like 3D printing (stereolithography) for artisanal metal work.

Another case was the project **Mate Bits Zaña**. Principal responsible for this project are Architects Roxana Garrido (Fab Academy 2012) and Jesus Peña Chavez. Fab Lab UNI was contacted in the process, but just

to present its services with the milling CNC machine, but not on the conceptualization and or implementation. This type of workshops is developed on a freer basis, depending on a particular assignment. On the issues regarding the beginning of the implementation, lack of resources, lack of access to machines, lack of diffusion and low participation were not hard to resolve. On the implementation and further workshops, lack of participation was not an issue at all, a fact that stands out from other projects in Peru, where normally the participation is low.

3.2 Case Study 2. Professional Practice, office or studio

Professionals establish a link with artisans to empower its work or use the artisan's object as a reference for new designs (neo artisan).

Ricardo Torres (Fab Academy 2014) through **Lima Makers** in Peru, developed the neo artisan production of the advertising company **Origen Peregrino**. A Peruvian design studio that merge the work of the agency TAG Estudio Gráfico and Lau Toyosato to redesign artisan pieces of Andean origin replacing materials and design in order to turn it into an artistic and commercial product.

3.3 Case Studies 3. Inside the Fab Academy, FAB Symposium or a workshop organized by a FAB LAB.

Before start the first Fab Lab and Fab Academy in the region, the first generation of Latin-Americans graduated from Instituto de Arquitectura Avanzada de Cataluña (IaaC) of Spain, with students from Peru, Colombia, Chile and Costa Rica. Between 2008 and 2017, 660 students graduated from FAB Academy, but only 86 (13%) are from a Latin American FabLab in Peru, Mexico, Chile, Ecuador and Costa Rica. Analyzing the final projects of graduates, we found that this is one space for empowerment of ideas for architects or designers related to craftsmanship. At **FAB Academies** developed between 2012 and 2014 there was a generation of students with projects aimed to the artisanal community, both individual and collective. This graduated students was Diego Machuca, Walter Gonzales and Roxana Garrido (2012); Gonzalo Pérez (2013); Vanessa Montezuma, Vaneza Caycho and Ricardo Torres (2014).

Architect Diego Edgardo Machuca Vargas (Fab Academy 2012) led **VCI - Vivienda Cinética Interactiva** along Universidad Ricardo Palma, making workshops of many sessions using bamboo along with the usual tools found in a Fab Lab, like the Shopbot, Laser cut machine and Roland Modela. The idea of the project was to create a house that could shift its shape based on solar patterns. This activity is no longer made, due mainly to lack of diffusion, and the possibility of having a space to make the activity with some continuity. One of the main things that stands out in this project as a support for artisans, is the ability to modify a process of creating and object and using programming to preserve the memory of it.

The network **Artesanías Digitales** started at FAB7 (2011), and begun with public activities in 2013. Formally presented at the **Red de Laboratorios de Fabricación Digital de Latinoamérica FAB LAT** in 2016, its initiatives promote the "Exchange of knowledge between craftsmen from different cultures and countries, on the impact that digital fabrication has in the production processes in the artisanal practice". This, among other self-helped experiences, was formalized the group **FABCraft** at FAB13 (2017), in Santiago de Chile. By 2018, these initiatives bring together different cases from Fab Labs in Mexico, Peru, Costa Rica and Brazil. Like the case of Fab Lab Ecuador and its **HeartMade** program that focuses on entrepreneurship and accelerated design for rural communities, focused on technology education and the development of contemporary products.

3.4 Case Study 4. Experiences developed by a Mobile Fab Lab or Universities.

In the last case, the Fab Labs going to their communities and establish a link with artisans.

According to Sperling et al. (2015), state and private universities in Latin America gather most of the digital fabrication laboratories. So, the Universidad Nacional de Ingeniería (Peru) and Addis-Ababa University (Ethiopia) were the two first hosts of the FAB Academy Project in the Global South. Financed by grant funds from their countries or universities, like the case of MIT in the USA, through NSF. In this category, we have experiences that try to alphabetize and get closer to a community, by exiting their premises and taking their infrastructure. These are known as mobile laboratories, which reach to a several types of users, especially outside the large cities where most FabLabs are installed. Between 2001 and 2004,

Learning Independence Networks (LIN) or Esperanza of MIT, empowered technology in countries over importing it from somewhere else, and allowed Instituto Tecnológico de Costa Rica, in Cartago to develop its project “Aprender Independencia” (Learning Independence) managed by Bakhtiar Mikhak. One of his initiatives was presented at FAB1 (2005) under the concept of **Fab Labs Camps**, including a Mobile Fab Lab to visit different schools in the region. In 2007, MIT developed its first **Mobile Fab Lab**, and between 2009 and 2015 four were built in society with counties and agents external to MIT. Morel et al. (2015:1) argue that “these spaces (Fab Labs) are doing a good job in their functions of accelerating collaborative innovation, (...) serving a privileged type of users and very often not SMEs”.

In France, in 2001, Université de Lorraine started the first **Mobile Fab Lab France** (2014) oriented to SME. With the same interest, **Fab Lab Movil Kolbi Veritas** was created, at Universidad Veritas de Costa Rica (2017). The access to communities through Mobile Fab Labs is a tendency. In this direction are working countries as México (Fab Lab Monterrey, Yucatán and Maya). In Colombia the Social Mobile Project was an initiative promoted Fab Lab Cali. **Fab Lab Yachay** from Ecuador and **TecLab** from Peru represent Andean initiatives in the region. With the same intention, initiatives like the **Floating Fab Lab Amazon** presented at FAB9 (2013) by Benito Juárez have the same scope: to reach out through technology and empower the handiwork of rural population. At FAB13 (2017) **Mobile LaT Labs Network** was an initiative driven by Robert Garita from Costa Rica (Fig. 1.).

Figure 1: Latin American Mobile Fab labs in 2018

In Latin America are another initiatives without support of Fab Labs but with the same intention are **Aconcagua Fab Lab** (Chile) and **Kombi Pronto 3D** (Brazil), this projects empowered to micro and small craftsmen.

4 Conclusions

4.1 Origins

Architecture seems to be the profession that relates the most to the investigations and projects presented at this research. One of the reasons is that in South America there is a population of Grad students specialised in digital fabrication, that came back from Europe and the USA during the first decade of the 21st century (Sperling et al., 2015), Implementing emergent technologies in their schools. Industrial

designers, on their part, re-appropriated traditional objects as references to establish new design lines, which opens to a new independent production line. We consider that the achieved results reveal that programming and fabrication have been relevant for artisans and has meant the learning of processes by architects and designers. This is a very important point since the synergy produced an incentive that made them think more about the process and not just about the object. Analysing other's process and rethinking it in order to produce code, opened the possibilities to upgrade new designs.

From this answers, we could think that the university itself seems to be the best scenario for creativity and openness to new ideas. More so even compared to being in an office or studio, perhaps because when we compare this data to the profession, we see that architects are more engaged than other professions. This fact leads to believe that an office or architectural studio generally does not leave much space for trying out new techniques or beginning a research.

An answer that seems a bit surprising is to see that being in the FAB Academy does not lead towards new sustainable projects. This could be because the program does not leave any extra time for doing anything more than the week's assignment. This does not mean creativity is not a key element of the FAB Academy. We believe that although the FAB Academy does not lead specifically towards the beginning of a project, it definitely gives the tools to finally achieving it.

4.2 Implementation and Scope

In the cases studied, the users establishing a link with a Fab Labs, rather than choosing an open talk or workshop. We can deduce from this approach the need to connect with associations already established to support its projects. Among the institutions that contributed, we can find several differences.

The connection with the local government is a feature important to impulse the artisan production, encouraging local traditions. The introduction of fabrication allowed to overcome the simple representation to which traditional artisans were used to, seeing in the result the possibility of reinventing their proposals.

The visits to the communities have had the highest impact on the other categories and the initiatives demonstrate a social interest above the economic, becoming an important foundation to strengthen local crafts.

5 Discussion: "Who should be resilient, against what, and how?"

Who should be resilient? In times of resilience, the analyzed cases demand the empowerment of formal and informal craftsmanship, which has a great potential for the south and its communities. On the other hand, scripting and programming guided by Fab Labs allowed the permanence of the design process in code, opening the possibilities to upgrade new designs. That is the reason why each fab lab must also increase its resilience, including the government in this task.

Against what? Lindtner & Avle (2017:12) state that "political leaders have been seizing opportunities linked to the promises of digital fabrication, pressing citizens to become self-entrepreneurial and by extension, collectively innovative". These promises produce a fictitious hope that has not had the support of the government, considering that the business models of the northern hemisphere are a starting point but not a solution for the region. Our challenge is to explore different ways of interaction between technology, our traditions and our environment. In July 2015, 574 Fab Labs were created and only 8% corresponded to South America (Herrera et al., 2015). By 2018, 14 Latin American countries and their 130 fablabs belong to a network of 1284 labs (an increase of 134% since 2015). Our region represents 10% of the global network and South America continues to maintain 8% after 3 years.

Without an adequate selection of the sector to empower, the increasing of Fab Labs in Latin America will keep on being affected by the lack of sustainability, so that they activating and deactivating through the years.

How? Programming demonstrated that facilitates the codification of processes and the artisan's know-how. Research on artisan local know-how and the customisation of the design process achieved by Latin American artisans in collaboration with Fab Labs will allow a closer relationship with computational

thought, which will give more importance to the process over the result. By learning design processes considering materials (wood, leather, clay, bronze, metal, porcelain, etc.), fabrication and joints, interacting the object scale in a computational environment, we will evolve to experiences in architectural scale. This gradual adaptation is sustainable since our economies do not allow educational investments in order to experiment directly with prototypes in architectural scale. Therefore, this approach to craft is an opportunity to understand processes in a formative way. This research provides experiences that could strengthen the identity of contemporary design in the region, driven by people directing educational programs, fabrication laboratories, workshops and government offices, taking popular traditions to a multidisciplinary systematized synergy. The Fab Labs together with the academic potential of their managers are one of the ways to strengthen resilient communities.

References

- Borges, A. (2011). *Design + Craft. The Brazilian Path*. Sao Paulo: Editora Terceiro Nome.
- Borges, A. (2013). Craft revitalization as a change agent in Latin America. *Making Futures Journal* 3, pp. 11-14. Retrieved 11 September 2017, from http://www.plymouthart.ac.uk/documents/Adelia_Borges_-_Keynote.pdf
- CNCA (2017). *Política de fomento para las artesanías 2017-2022*. Valparaíso, Chile: Consejo Nacional de la Cultura y las Artes. Retrieved 3 March 2018, from http://www.cultura.gob.cl/politicas-culturales/wp-content/uploads/sites/2/2017/01/politica_artesania.pdf
- DIRCETUR (2016). *Plan operativo institucional 2016*. Puno, Perú: Dirección Regional de Comercio Exterior y Turismo.
- Duque, C., Sethi, R. & Vencatachellum, I. (2005). *Designers meet Artisans*. Nueva Dehli: Craft Revival Trust.
- Fountain, W. (2013). Resurgent Homecraft, Design for Resilience, and the Everyday Practices of Sustainable Living. *Making Futures Journal* 3. Retrieved 12 May 2017, from http://makingfutures.plymouthart.ac.uk/media/75788/fountain__wendy_paper.pdf
- García, N. (2004). *Diferentes, desiguales y desconectados. Mapas de la interculturalidad*. Barcelona: Gedisa.
- Gershenfeld, N. (2005). *Fab: The Coming Revolution on Your Desktop—from Personal Computers to Personal Fabrication*. New York: Basic Books.
- Gershenfeld, N. (2012) How to make Almost Anything. *The Digital Fabrication Revolution*. *Foreign Affairs* 91(6), pp. 43-57. Retrieved 12 December 2017, from <http://cba.mit.edu/docs/papers/12.09.FA.pdf>
- Herrera, P. (2012) Reusing codes as a mechanism of information and cognition: Scripting in architecture. Paper presented at the 16th SIGraDi. Retrieved 30 November 2012, from http://papers.cumincad.org/cgi-bin/works/Show?sigradi2012_235
- Herrera, P. (2016) Digital Fabrication and Revival Craft in Latin America. Paper presented at 10th ICDHS 2016, Taipei, China. Retrieved 15 December 2016, from http://pdf.blucher.com.br.s3-sa-east-1.amazonaws.com/designproceedings/icdhs2016/03_019.pdf
- Herrera, P. (2016b) Artesanía en Latinoamérica. Experiencias en el contexto de la Fabricación Digital. Paper presented at the 20th SIGraDi. Retrieved 12 March 2018 from <http://pdf.blucher.com.br.s3-sa-east-1.amazonaws.com/designproceedings/sigradi2016/814.pdf>
- Herrera, P. & Juárez, B. (2013). Fabrication Laboratories: Problems and possibilities of implementation in Latin America. Paper presented at the 9th International Fab Lab Conference, FAB9, Yokohama, Japan, 21-27 August 2013. Retrieved 12 January 2014, from <http://hdl.handle.net/10757/605215>
- Herrera, P. Sperling, D., & Scheeren, R. (2015). Independent Laboratories of Fabrication in Latin America. Paper presented at the 11th International Fab Lab Conference, FAB11, Cambridge, MIT. Retrieved 18 March 2016, from https://archive.org/download/Fab11Paper20/Fab11_paper_20.pdf
- Jacobs, J. (2013). *Algorithmic Craft: the Synthesis of computational Design, Digital Fabrication, and Hand Craft*. MIT MSc in Media Arts and Sciences thesis.
- Kinnunen, N. (2015). Craft beyond craft: the transformative role of craft's resilience. *Making Futures Journal* 4. Retrieved 16 January 2018, from <http://makingfutures.plymouthart.ac.uk/media/75744/nora-kinnunen.pdf>
- Kornhauser, D. (2002). *Designing a Craft Computing Environment for Non-Industrial Settings*. MIT MSc in Media Arts and Sciences thesis.

- Pablo C. Herrera, Vanessa Montezuma, Benito Juárez: Crafts in Latin America: The contribution of the Fab Labs in the promotion of resilient communities
- Lassiter, S. (2013). FabLabs: Thoughts and Remembrances. In J. W.-H. Buching (Ed.), *FabLabs of Machines, Makers and Inventors* (pp. 249-257). Wetzlar: Majuskel Medienproduktion GmbH.
- Lauer, M. (1982). *Crítica de la artesanía. Plástica y sociedad en los andes peruanos*. Lima: DESCO.
- Lindtner, S. & Avle, S. (2017). Tinkering with Governance: Technopolitics and the Economization of Citizenship. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction*, Volume 1, Issue CSCW, Article No. 70. Retrieved 17 January 2018, from <https://doi.org/10.1145/3134705>
- Mboa, T. (2017). Benefits and the hidden face of the maker movement: Thoughts on its appropriation in African context. *LIINC* 13(1), pp. 72-88. Retrieved 13 March 2018, from <https://doi.org/10.18617/liinc.v13i1.3774>
- Morel, L., Dupont, L., & Pascal, H. (2015). When innovation supported by Fab Labs become a tool for the territorial economic development: Example of the first Mobile Fab Lab in France. *Proceedings of the International Association for Management of Technology*. Retrieved 22 March 2018, from <http://www.agefa.org/acteurs-des-territoires/wp-content/uploads/sites/6/2015/06/iamot-nomadlab-2015.pdf>
- Rengifo, A. (1989). *La artesanía en la obra de José Sabogal Wiesse*. Lima: Centro de Proyectos Integrales.
- Sabogal, J. (13 de Noviembre de 1974). *Artesano y Artesanías*. *Diario El Comercio*.
- Seo-Zindy, R., & Heeks, R. (2017). Researching the Emergence of 3D Printing, Makerspaces, Hackerspaces and Fab Labs in the Global South: A scoping review and research agenda on digital innovation and fabrication networks. *Electronic Journal of Information Systems in Developing Countries*, 80(5), pp. 1-24. Retrieved 16 March 2018, from <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.1681-4835.2017.tb00589.x>
- Sperling, D., Herrera, P., & Scheeren, R. (2015). Migratory Movements of Homo Faber: Mapping Fab Labs in Latin America. Paper presentet at Computer-Aided Architectural Design Futures. *The Next City - New Technologies and the Future of the Built Environment CAAD Futures 2015*. *Communications in Computer and Information Science*, vol 527. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. Retrieved 31 July 2015, from https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-47386-3_22
- Troxler, P. (2010). Commons-based Peer-Production of Physical Goods Is there Room for a Hybrid Innovation Ecology?. Paper presented at the 3rd Free Culture Research Conference, Berlin, October 8-9, 2012. Retrieved 11 September 2010, from https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/Papers.cfm?abstract_id=1692617
- Waldman-Brown A., Obeng GY., Adu-Gyamfi Y., Langevin S., & Adam A. (2013) *Fabbing for Africa's Informal Sector*. Paper presentet at the 9th International Fab Lab Conference, FAB9, Yokohama, Japan, 21-27 August 2013. Retrieved 18 December 2017, from <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.635.8804&rep=rep1&type=pdf>